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Review Article

**CURRENT SCENARIO OF PHARMACEUTICAL & HERBAL
MEDICINES & FUTURE PROSPECTUS WORLD WIDE:
AN OVERVIEW**Ankita S.Sarnaik¹, Pragati S.Shinde², Swati P.Deshmukh³¹Lecturer, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim²Assistant Professor, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim³Professor, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim**Abstract:**

Plants are knowingly or unknowingly helping the living beings since the beginning of civilization. Although new and new diseases are getting discovered day by day, creator had provided us with most of the cure in the form of medicinal plants. Herbs as a raw material. India is the country of herbs, and the Indian traditional treatment system was also based on herbs and medicinal plant that is known as Ayurveda. India is the well-known mine of well-recorded herbal plants with their medicinal Use. Herbal medicine is also called botanical medicines or phytomedicine. Herb are extract from natural origin which is derived from algae fungi and lichens and higher plants such as leaves stem fruit flower seeds and roots etc. Herbal drug Industry is undergoing a major change with respect to domestic and global requirements. Herbal medicine and treatment with herbs are not new to humanity, and it has been in practice since thousands of years back and still going on. Nutraceuticals is the fastest growing herbal components due to increase in day to day lifestyle concern among global population. Along with the increased global and domestic essentiality of evidence based reports on safety, efficacy and kinetics of herbal products, scientific technicality and involvement of trained human resource should be promoted in the site of herbal drug Manufacturing. This review focuses on the recent various important challenges in quality evaluation of medicinal plants in the authenticity, efficacy, Toxicity and consistency. In a survey report of the world Health Organization, it was found that the 80% population of the world rely on traditional herbal medicine for primary health-care need.

Keywords: Folk medicines, chronic disease, medicines Herbal Technology, Herbal drugs, Herbs, AYUSH, Herbal drug, Nutraceuticals, Drug industry

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INTRODUCTION:

Nature is always a golden sign to show the prominent Phenomena of coexistence. Natural products from Plants, animals and minerals are the basis for treating Human diseases. Medicinal plants are presently in Demand and their acceptance is increasing progressively. Undoubtedly, plants play an important role by providing Essential services in ecosystems. Without plants, humans And other living organisms cannot Live in a way living Should be Medicinal plants are used for treatment Because they have certain Properties, including synergistic Actions. The constituents of the plant may interact With each other, and this interaction can be beneficial For both or adverse to either of them or eliminate the Harmful effects of both. Plant-derived compounds can Dramatically improve hard-to-treat illnesses, such as Cancer. Plant components are also characterized by their Ability to prevent the development of certain diseases. The toxicity and adverse effects of conventional and Allopathic medicines have also been important factors in The sudden increase in population demands and increase In the number of herbal drug manufactures as well as a Reduction in the use of chemical drugs. Knowing the history of any science is effective in Understanding and using that science. More than A tenth of the plant species (over 50 000 species) are used In pharmaceutical and cosmetic products. However, the Distribution of medicinal plants across the World is not Uniform (5,6), and medicinal herbs are mainly collected From the wildlife population. Indeed, the demand for Wildlife sources has increased by 8%-15% per year in Europe, North America and Asia in recent decades. The term medicinal plant refers to a variety of plants that Have medicinal Properties. These plants are a rich source Of compounds that can be used to develop drug synthesis .The parts of medicinal plants that may be used are Different types of seeds, root, leaf, fruit, skin, flowers or Even the whole plant. The active compounds in most parts Of the medicinal plants have direct or indirect therapeutic Effects and are used as medicinal agents. In the body of These plants, certain materials are Produced and stored That are referred to as active compounds (substances), Which have physiological effects on the living organisms .Human is mainly dependent on raw plant materials In order to meet medical needs to maintain health and Cure diseases. Knowing the history of any science is effective in Understanding and using that science. Hence, the Historical significance of the past and present and Future To medicinal herbs will continue to be addressed. In this Perspective review, we have highlighted and discussed The history, current challenges,

development and future Outlook of using medicinal plants and their active Compound.

Historical Background

Natural product coming from natural sources like plants was used by human beings over the years as food and medicines, especially plants parts or whole plant to cure and prevent disease. It is very much difficult to calculate the exact time when people started using plants as medicine, but some ancient literature and other sources are available which promises its start. The oldest written evidence related to the use of medicinal plants for the preparation of drugs has been found on a Sumerian clay slab from Nagpur which is approximately 5000 years old. It comprised Of 12 recipes for drug preparation and referring to over 250 various plants, some of them alkaloid such as poppy, henbane, and mandrake. The Indian holy books Vedas mention treatment with The help of plants, which are present in abundance in the country. The Chinese book based on the use of roots and grasses "Pen T' Sao," written by Emperor Shen Nung circa 2500 BC, treats 365 Drugs (dried parts of medicinal plants), many of which are being used nowadays. Theophrastus (371–287 BC) led the foundation of botanical science through his books "De Causis Plantarum"- Plant Etiology and "De Historia Plantarum" – Plant History. In these books, he Created a classification of about 500 medicinal plants known at the time. In the description of the plant toxicity action, Theophrastus underscored the important feature for humans to become familiar to them by a gradual increase in the doses. Each country has their own document regarding the use of Plants and herbs as medicine for treatment and cure of disease, and they differ from each other. In India, Ayurveda is the oldest System of medicine that is about 5000 years old. The Ayurveda text is actually the part of Atharvaveda which was in 1000 BC. In ancient time, it was transferred orally, and the first Ayurvedic text book was written and preserved in Sanskrit. Instead of fighting With disease ancient Ayurveda was meant essentially to promote Health. Main text available regarding herbal medicine is Charak Samhita (1000 BC) and Sushrut Samhita (100 AD). Ayurveda text medica provides detailed descriptions of more than 1500 herbs and 10, 000 formulations. Diagnostics features along with signs and symptoms of over 5000 diseases or disorders are described in Madhav Nidan (800 AD).

There are eight branches in the Ayurvedic study, and these are as follows:

- Kaya Chikitsa (general medicine),
- Kaumara Bhruthya (pediatrics),

- Bhutha Vidhya (psychiatry),
- Salakya (ENT and ophthalmology and dentistry),
- Shalya (surgery),
- Agada Tantra (toxicology),
- Rasayana (rejuvenation therapy), and
- Vajeeekarana (sexual vitality).

Hippocrates, father of medicines, worked mainly on Anatomy and Physiology of human being and wrote more than 60 medicinal books. He also postulated a humoral theory that explains that human body consists of four humor blood, phlegm, yellow bile, And black bile which are mainly responsible for the functioning of the body in healthy condition as well as in diseases. Hippocrates only used herb and is best known for saying; "Let your food be your medicine and let medicine be your food," "Sickness is caused by body's inability to digest its environment". The early 19th century is denoted as the turning point in the field of use and application related to medicinal plant. The discovery, Substantiation, and isolation of alkaloids from poppy (1806) and other plants. In the meanwhile, the isolation of glycosides marked the beginning of scientific pharmacy. With the enhancement and Upgradation of the chemical methods, other active substances from medicinal plants were also discovered.

Research and manufacturing organization related to Medicinal Plants in India :-

- 1) CCRAS(Central council for Research in ayurveda and Siddha - New Delhi
- 2) RRL(Regional Research Laboratory)(CSIR) - Jammu-Tawi
- 3) NBRI(National Botanical Research Institute)(CSIR)- Lucknow
- 4) Bhavan ;s SPARC -Mumbai
- 5) National Institute of Ayurveda - Jaipur
- 6) Banaras Hindu University -Varanasi
- 7) CIMAP(Central Institute for Medicinal and Aromatic Plants)- Lucknow
- 8) ICMR(Indian council of Medical research_) -New Delhi
- 9))PERDCentre(Pharmaceutical Education and research Development)- Ahmedabad
- 10) CCRUM(Central Council for Research in Unani medicine) -New Delhi
- 11) IHMMR(Indian Institute of History of Medicine and Medical Research)-New Delhi
- 12) Zandu Foundation -Mumbai
- 13) Pharmexcil- Hyderabad
- 14) Chemexcil - Mumbai
- 15) CDRI(Centrral Drug Research Institute)(CSIR)-Luckno

- 16) National Chemical laboratory :- Pune
- 17) NPRC(Nicholas Piramal Research center) :- Mumbai
- 18)

Future prospects of herbal medicine market:

Almost, 70% modern medicines in India are Derived from natural products. The basic uses of plants in medicine will continue in the Future, as a source of therapeutic agents, and as raw material base for the extraction of semisynthetic chemical compounds such as cosmetics, perfumes and food industries. Popularity of Healthcare plant-derived products has been traced to their increasing acceptance and use in the cosmetic industry as well as to increasing public costs in the maintenance of Personal health and well being. In the dual role as a source of healthcare and income, Medicinal plants make an important contribution to the larger development process. Though The efficacy of herbal requires development of quality consciousness in respect of the Evaluation related evidences, supplying the demand for botanicals and herbals is a booming Business. Recently even developed countries, are using medicinal systems that involve the Use of herbal drugs and remedies. Undoubtedly the demand for plant derived products has Increased worldwide. The demand is estimated to Grow in the years to come fuelled by the Growth of sales of herbal supplements and remedies. This means that scientists, doctors and Pharmaceutical companies will be looking at countries like China, India, etc. For their Requirements, as they have the most number of medicinal plant species and are the top Exporters of medicinal plants. Future is in the phase of increasing demand and fast-growing Market of herbal medicines and other herbal healthcare products, In both developing and developed countries of the world.

HISTORY OF HERBAL MATERIAL

Ayurveda, Unani, Siddha, and homoeopathy (AYUSH) pharmaceuticals are among the herbal exports, which make about 3% of all Indian pharmaceutical exports. 70% of the exports from the herbal industry, which are projected to be valued Rs. 10 billion year, are made up of raw materials. More than 70% of India's 1.1 billion population still use these non-allopathic systems of medicine. Currently, there is no separate category of herbal drugs or dietary Supplements, as per the Indian Drugs Act. However, there is a vast experiential-evidence base for many of the natural drugs. In the 21st century, with the increased efficacy in pharmacological effects of medicinal plants, herbal medicine has been considered as a promising future medicine for the management of health care. Acharya Charak, who was

born around 300 BC, was a vital contributor to Ayurveda's ancient art and science, medicine, and lifestyle system that originated in ancient India. Acharya Charak was designated as the Father of Medicine. His well-known book, the 'Samhita Charak,' is regarded as an Ayurvedic encyclopaedia. Of 48,655 plant species documented (including virus, bacteria, algae, fungi and lichens) 9,500 species have ethno-botanical importance and 7,500 species are in medicinal use for indigenous health practices as well as modern system of medicines. The global Herbal medicine market size was valued at USD 201.06 billion in 2022 and is projected to grow from USD 216.40 billion in 2023 to USD 371.45 billion by 2030, exhibiting a CAGR of 8.02% during the forecast period. Europe Dominated the global market with a share of 45.08% in 2022.

Herbal drugs Biological name/Family Chemical constituents Uses:

Sr no	Common name	Botanical name	Part used	Family	Uses
1.	Tulsi	Ocimum sanctum	Leaves	Labiatae	Antipyretic; Antitussive
2.	Neem	Azadirachta indica	Leaves	Meliaceae	Antipyretic
3.	Brahmi	Centella asiatica	Whole plant	Umbellifera	Antipyretic; Blood purifier
4.	Amla	Emblica officinalis	Fruits	Euphorbiaceae	Antipyretic
5.	Dhaniya	Coriandrum sativum	Leaves, seeds	Umbelliferae	Antipyretic; Carminative
6.	Satavari	Asparagus adscendens	Tuberous Roots	Liliaceae	Antipyretic; Demulscient; Nutritive Tonic
7.	Bahera	Terminalia bellerica	Fruits	Combretaceae	Antipyretic; Expectorant
8.	Cinchona	Cinchona officinalis	Bark seed	Rubiaceae	Antipyretic;
9.	Bhindi	Abelmoschus esculentus	Fruits	Malvaceae	Antipyretic, Diuretic
10.	Imli	Tamarindus indica	Wood, volatile oil	Caesalpiniaceae	Antipyretic; Carminative
11.	Swetchandan	Santalum album	Fruits	Santalaceae	Antipyretics; Sedative
12.	Palwal	Santalum album	Roots; Flower; Fruits; Bark	Cucurbitaceae	Antipyretic; Laxative
13.	Nirgandi	Vitex negundo	Dried roots	Verbenaceae	Antipyretic; Astringent
14.	Bish	Aconitum ferox	Leaves; Bark; Milky Juice	Ranunculaceae	Antipyretic
15.	Datyuni	Alstonia scholaris	Stem; Leaves; Root	Apocynaceae	Antipyretic; Stimulant

16.	Gulancha	Cocculus cordifolia	Stem	Menispermaceae	Antipyretic; Aphrodisiac
17.	Jharhaldi	Coscinum fenestratum	Leaves, roots	Menispermaceae	Antipyretic; Stomachic
18.	Phalakantak	Daemia extensa	Dried roots	Ascepiadaceae	Antipyretic; Expectorant
19.	Kali mirch	Piper nigrum	Roots	Piperaceae	Antipyretic; Carminative
20.	Chitravalli	Rubiaceae cordifolia	Roots	Rubiaceae	Antipyretic; Astringent
21.	Jwaranthakah	Swertia chirata	Whole Herb	Gentianaceae	Antipyretic; Antidot
22.	Gurach	Tinospora cordifolia	Stem; Root	Menispermaceae	Antipyretic; Antidot
23.	Jangalilahun	Allium sativum	Bulb, oil	Liliaceae	Antipyretic; Antiseptic
24.	Kasondi	Cassia occidentalis	Leaves; Seeds; Root	Caesalpiniaceae	Antipyretic; Purgative
25.	Bhringraj	Eclipta erecta	Roots, leaves	Compositae	Antipyretic; Emetic
26.	Akasbel	Cuscuta reflexa	Seeds; Stem; Fruits	Convolvulaceae	Antipyretic; Carminative
27.	Aghata	Achyranthes aspera	Leaves, seed, roots	Amarantaceae	Antipyretic; Astringent
28.	Cashew	Anacardium occidentale	Fruit, seed, bark, oil	Anacardiaceae	Antipyretic; Irritant;
29.	Ganja	Cannabis sativa	Leaves;	Cannabaceae	Antipyretic; Analgesic

• Future investigation of tribal medicines :

Tribal healers in most of the countries, where ethno medical treatment is frequently used to Treat cut wounds, skin infection, swelling, aging, mental illness, cancer, asthma, diabetes, Jaundice, scabies, eczema, venereal diseases, snakebite and gastric ulcer, provide instructions To local people as how to prepare medicine from herbal. They keep no records and the Information is mainly passed on verbally from generation to gene. World Health Organization (WHO) has shown great interest in documenting the use of medicinal plants Used by tribal from different parts of the world. Many developing countries have intensified Their efforts in documenting the ethno medical data on medicinal plants. Research to find out Scientific evidence for claims by tribal healers on Indian herbs has been intensified. Once These local ethno medical preparations are scientifically evaluated and disseminated properly, People will be better informed regarding efficacious drug treatment and improved health status.

• Industry:

In India, above 10,000 industrialized units are present for traditional Medicines and make around 1 billion US dollars net income using ISM And Herbal systems. AYUSH manufacturing units statistically showed Steady annual growth in drug production

since last two decades. Ayurvedic preparations are available in both classical forms (tablets, Powder, medicated oil, decoction, fermented products and medicated Ghee) and new drug forms like lotions, capsules, syrups, liniments, Ointments, granules and creams etc. The manufacturing process in this Field is regulated by Drugs and Cosmetic act (1940) and rules (1945). GMP as well as GLP for Indian system of medicines have been defined By the governing authorities, which to be followed by organizations,Involved in the manufacturing of traditional and herbal drugs.[36] Education and Practice CCIM (Central Council of Indian Medicine) is tangled with regulation Of education.

CONCLUSION:

Herbal medicines are the synthesis of therapeutic experiences of generations of practicing physicians of indigenous systems of medicine for over hundreds of years. Herbal medicines are now in great demand in the developing World for primary health care not because they are inexpensive but also for better cultural acceptability, better compatibility with the human body and minimal side effects. However, recent findings indicate that all herbal Medicines may not be safe as severe consequences are reported for some herbal drugs. Most herbal products on the market today have not been subjected to drug approval process to demonstrate their safety and effectiveness. Thousand years of traditional use can provide us with valuable guidelines to the selection, preparation and Application of herbal formulation. To be accepted as viable alternative to modern medicine, the same vigorous Method of scientific and clinical validation must be applied to prove the safety and effectiveness of a therapeutical product. In the present review we attempted to describe the present scenario and project the future of herbal Medicine. Several drugs have entered the International market through study of Ethnopharmacology aan Traditional medicine. Cosmeceuticals are the products that forms Interconnect between the drug and cosmetics. Cosmeceuticals are found to be a new rising market Not only for males but also for females. Nutraceuticals have established health benefits and Their utilization will keep diseases away and allow Humans to sustain an overall good health. There is Rich biodiversity of medicinal plants worldwide Where many species of both medicinal and Biopesticides plants are utilized. There is a Necessary to educate and sensitize the younger age Group on the Potential and importance of Conserving the local biodiversity, native knowledge And practices.

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